

Title: First results from a survey concerning older adults' engagement with Digital Heritage through XR

Abstract:

The rapid growth of digital heritage and immersive technologies like Extended Reality (XR) presents both opportunities and challenges, especially for older adults. While these technologies offer new ways to experience cultural and historical content, there is a gap in understanding how older adults interact with, understand, and are impacted by digital heritage within XR environments. This gap highlights a need for research that focuses on the accessibility, usability, and emotional engagement of older adults with digital heritage in XR.

Addressing this challenge, this paper presents a comprehensive survey aimed at exploring older adults' engagement with digital heritage in XR spaces. By reviewing current literature and categorizing findings, we highlight how older adults experience these technologies, from navigating and interpreting digital content to their emotional and cognitive responses. This work seeks to bridge the relevant knowledge gap by offering insights into the design and implementation of XR applications that are more accessible and meaningful to older adults. This research contributes to the ongoing discourse on making digital heritage experiences inclusive and enriching for all ages, particularly focusing on optimizing XR environments for older adult users.

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